

Protocol for Field Monitoring of Cardiac Activity in Intertidal Mussels Using the Pulse Device

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1. State-of-the-art

Mussels are among the most important habitat-forming bivalves in coastal ecosystems, acting as ecosystem engineers that increase substrate complexity, retain moisture, buffer temperature extremes, and support associated biodiversity (Gutiérrez et al., 2003; O'Brien & Scheibling, 2018). In rocky intertidal habitats, however, mussels are also regularly exposed to strong environmental fluctuations associated with tidal cycles, especially during low tide, when aerial exposure increases the risk of desiccation and thermal stress (Helmuth et al., 2006; Seabra et al., 2016; Chapperon et al., 2017). Because of their ecological importance, broad distribution, and sensitivity to environmental change, mussels are widely used as model organisms and bioindicators in coastal monitoring and climate-change research (Thyrring et al., 2015; Somero, 2010).

At the individual level, cardiac activity is considered a reliable physiological indicator of organismal condition in intertidal invertebrates, particularly molluscs (Chelazzi et al., 2001; Marshall et al., 2011). Heartbeat monitoring under natural and controlled conditions provides valuable information on short-term responses to environmental stressors, species interactions, and toxic exposure (Stillman & Somero, 1996; Chelazzi et al., 2004). This is especially relevant in intertidal systems, where many organisms already live close to their physiological tolerance limits (Somero, 2002).

Methods for cardiac monitoring have evolved from invasive approaches, such as electrode implantation in the pericardial cavity (Helm & Trueman, 1967), to non-invasive infrared-based systems that detect cardiac movements externally through the shell (Burnett et al., 2013). These systems allow real-time physiological monitoring with minimal disturbance to the animal, making them particularly suitable for ecological applications in mussels under natural intertidal conditions (Burnett et al., 2013; Gandra et al., 2015).

2. Objectives

The objective of this protocol is to provide a standardized field method for non-invasive recording of cardiac activity in intertidal mussels using the field-Pulse device (Fig.1) during low tide. The protocol is intended to support consistent acquisition of heart beat records under natural shore conditions, allowing comparisons among individuals, sites, and contrasting microhabitats.

Figure 1: Field-PULSE device used for non-invasive recording of cardiac activity in intertidal mussels under natural shore conditions. Photo by: Mar Humet

3. Equipment and Materials

- field-PULSE device
- Waterproof sensor for PULSE
- Smartphone
 - Pulse App (v3.7)
- Blue Tack (Bostik)
- Callipers

Study area and sampling conditions

Cardiac activity measurements should be conducted in rocky intertidal habitats during low tide, when mussels are exposed and accessible for sensor placement. Measurements should preferably be performed under calm field conditions that allow stable positioning of the sensor and safe handling of the equipment.

Data recorded during each measurement

In addition to heart rate, the following environmental and biological variables should be recorded for each individual in the Pulse App (Fig.2):

- Exposure category (hot: south-facing; cold: north-facing);

- Species;
- Shore level: T (top), M (mid) or L (low) (Fig.3);
- Position relative to water: O (Out of the water);
- Temperature;
- Individual size (shell length, cm).

Figure 2: Pulse App (version 3.7) interface used for real-time recording and storage of mussel cardiac activity during field measurements.

Figure 3: Image from Mindelo, Portugal, showing the distinct vertical zonation typical of rocky intertidal shores. In the top zone, organisms are less abundant due to generally harsher environmental conditions. In the mid-intertidal of the NE Atlantic, mussel beds typically dominate. In the lower intertidal, biodiversity is higher, often with a wide variety of algal species prevailing. Photo by: Gabriela Borer

Field procedure for cardiac activity recording

Mussel selection criteria

Only mussels firmly attached to the substrate and showing no visible shell damage should be selected for measurement. Individuals heavily covered by epibionts or debris in the sensor placement area should be avoided when these interfere with signal acquisition.

Sensor placement

The sensor was placed on the anterior-left dorsal region of the shell, a location selected based on the internal anatomy of mussels (Fig.4). In mussels, the heart lies dorsally and slightly anterior within the pericardial cavity, providing a reliable external reference point for sensor positioning and cardiac signal detection (Bayne, 1976; Gosling, 1992).

Figure 4: Reference for sensor placement during field cardiac activity measurements in mussels. The sensor is positioned on the anterior-left dorsal region of the shell, corresponding to the anatomical location of the heart and allowing non-invasive detection of cardiac signals.

Signal stabilization

After sensor placement, a stabilization period of approximately 30-50 seconds should be allowed before starting the recording to ensure proper signal acquisition.

Recording

Cardiac activity should then be recorded continuously for 60 seconds per individual using Pulse App (v3.7). If the signal is unstable or unclear, the sensor should be repositioned and the stabilization step repeated before starting a new recording. Measurements with poor contact or interrupted signals should be flagged in the field notes.

4. Data management and storage

After each measurement, the cardiac activity recording should be saved immediately in the Pulse App. At the end of each field session, all files should be exported and transferred to a computer for storage and backup. Each recording must be associated with a unique identifier linking the physiological file to its corresponding metadata record. A standardized naming format is recommended, including site, date, individual code, and exposure category.

Metadata should be compiled in a structured table and saved in widely accessible formats such as .csv or .xlsx. At minimum, this table should include: site, date, time, species, individual code, exposure category, shore level, position relative to water, temperature, and shell length. These tabular formats facilitate data organization, later inspection, and integration with other environmental or biological datasets.

After transfer, all recordings should be checked to confirm file integrity, correct metadata association, and acceptable signal quality. Files with unstable signals, incomplete records, or unclear identification should be flagged for later review. For long-term organization, files should be stored in a structured folder system by site and date, and at least one backup copy should be created. Metadata tables should be archived together with the physiological records to ensure traceability and future reuse of the dataset.

5. References

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